

Role of DRDA in Rural Development in Haryana

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ABSTRACT

Rural development is conceived as strategy aimed at finding ways to improve the rural lives with participation of the rural people themselves so as to meet the required need of the rural area. According to World Bank (2005), rural development is the process of rural modernization and the monetization of the rural society leading to its transition from traditional isolation to integration with the national economy. Also, rural development is perceived as a process of not only increasing the level of per capital income in the rural areas but also the standard of living of the rural population measured by food and nutrition level, health education, housing, recreation and security. Haryana is a leading contributor to the country's production of food grain and milk.. Greening rural development can stimulate rural economies, create jobs and help maintain critical ecosystem services and strengthen climate resilience of the rural people. Conversely, environmental challenges can limit the attainment of development goal. The basic objective of this paper is to upgrade the living standard of the rural people by providing ways to develop rural parts of Haryana and improving food security including those below poverty line (BPL) by restricting the rural-urban migration. However, to provide optimum benefit to the grass-root level, there is a need for coordination among various Government agencies and other institutions engaged in rural development. This will also assist in minimizing the rural-urban gap in terms of basic infrastructure facilities essential for 'Sustainable Development' of a settlement.

Key words - Rural Development, Growth Rate, Literacy Rate, district rural development agency

INTRODUCTION

Rural development is the process of improving the quality of life and economic well-being of people living in relatively isolated and sparsely populated areas. Rural development has traditionally centered on the exploitation of land-intensive natural resources such as agriculture and forestry. However, changes in global production networks and increased urbanization have changed the character of rural areas. Rural development as a concept suggests the overall development of the areas and sustaining improvement in the quality of life of rural people. It results in creating an 2 environment conducive to improve people's capacity and to utilize it fully, without exploitation, on a sustainable basis. It is both the means and end of economic development of a country like India. Today, apart from governments, rural development has become a matter of interest to industrialists, financiers, bankers and philanthropists as well. In India, a country of villages, it means making the life of the majority, worth to live and thus paying back them the dividend of India's economic growth.

Four decades of regulations and two decades of liberalization, has made India the ninth largest economy in the world (World Bank, 2011), which could grow, second after China, at an average rate of 8.46 per cent, for the last five years, even in the aftermath of global economic slowdown (Economic Survey, 2010-11). There are predictions that if the current high growth continues, India will overtake Japan (pre-quake) by 2030 (Economic Outlook – India 2008 to 2010). Today India hosts 11 per cent of the world's richest (Forbes India Magazine 2010) and it is looking forward the fortunes to trickle down to the rural people. India has 6.4 lakhs villages with a population of 83.3 crores which is 68.84% of the whole India (Census India, 2011). Providing timely and adequate cheap credit to farmers, rural artisans, petty shop keepers, and micro and small entrepreneurs is of paramount importance. It is reported that rural India suffers from a more serious lack of finance than urban Indian (Bose, 2004, Shah et al., 2007, Mishra, 2008, Remesha, 2003). Rural development strategies are a critical component of an inclusive growth strategy for Haryana.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

J. Dean Jansma and Frank M. Goode, Rural Development Research: "Conceptualizing and Measuring Key Concepts" In this research paper the researcher explain the conceptual basis for rural economic development. He said rural economic development is assumed to be reflected by increase in employment and/or income. The major determinants of income and employment in a given economic space (a rural community) are the quantity of the goods and services

sold to and inputs purchased from outside the community and the extent to which dollars entering the local area are "recirculated" within the local economy.

Kenneth L. Deavers," Social Science Contributions to Rural Development Policy in the 1980s". In this research paper author said, rural development policy involves deliberate action by federal, state, and local governments and private institutions and individuals to achieve three goals: (a) improved rural income levels and employment opportunities; (b) improved access by rural residents to adequate housing and essential community facilities and services; and (c) responsible use of rural resources and the rural environment to preserve the quality of rural life. In attempting to achieve these rural development goals, federal policy needs to be guide.

Clark Edwards," The Political Economy of Rural Development: Theoretical Perspectives". In this paper the author said that the rural and urban sectors of the economy are strongly interlinked. Growth in one sector impacts on the other. The growth process does not appear to be an equilibrium one in which marginal adjustments to opportunity costs eliminates disparities. This rural-urban imbalance is of national concern. It appears to have resulted in relatively densely populated cities and sparsely populated countryside. Rural development can increase economic efficiency, add to the nation's goods and services, and enhance the social and economic well-being of both the rural and the urban sectors.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To upgrade the living standard of the rural people by providing ways to develop rural parts of Haryana.
2. To know various schemes made by government of Haryana for developing its rural areas.
3. To provide optimum measures for restricting rural- urban migration.

RURAL DEVELOPMENT

In the last thirty years Asia has experienced dynamic growth and structural transformation, and has achieved substantial poverty reduction. The incidence of people living in poverty fell from more than 50 percent in the mid-1970s to 18 percent in 2004, and the incidence of hunger fell to 16 percent. However, Asia is still home to more than half of the world's poor, the majority of whom live in rural areas. Agricultural and rural development thus remains a critical component of an inclusive growth strategy for the region. Haryana is a leading contributor to the country's production of food grain and milk. Agriculture is the leading occupation for the residents of the state; the flat arable land is irrigated by submersible pumps and an extensive canal system. Haryana contributed heavily to the Green Revolution in the 1960's, that made India self-sufficient in food production. According to census, 1991-2001 about 71.07% of Haryana's population was living in rural area and the agricultural sector contributed 31.19% (Rs. 16625.71 crores) to the Net State Domestic Product. For the year 2006-07 this figure dropped to 21.45% (Rs. 24795.16 crores) which shows decline in the agriculture and animal husbandry sectors. Land, the main asset in rural area, is concentrated amongst a few.

The Population of Haryana according to the 2011 census stands at about 25 million, making it the 17th most populated state in India. The state lies in the northern part of the country and is well connected to the capital of India. There is a huge influx of population into Gurgaon, which is a part of Haryana from Delhi. The state is spread over an area of about 44000sq. km. making it the 20th largest state in the country in terms of area. The density of population per sq. Km. is about 570 which is above the national average. The state has a growth rate of about 19% which slightly exceeds the national growth rate of about 17%. The population of the state is rising considerably due to rapid efforts towards development and progress. The literacy rate in the state is about 76% a figure that has improved tremendously in the last few years due to the consistent efforts of the government. The sex ratio in Haryana leaves a lot to be desired as it lags behind the national average by 70 points. The statistics in the Haryana Census 2011 reveal facts that can be instrumental in planning for a better development plan for the state.

Haryana Population 2011

As per details from Census 2011, Haryana has population of 2.54 Crores, an increase from figure of 2.11 Crore in 2001 census. Total population of Haryana as per 2011 census is 25,351,462 of which male and female are 13,494,734 and 11,856,728 respectively. In 2001, total population was 21,144,564 in which males were 11,363,953 while females were 9,780,611.

(a) Haryana Population Growth Rate

The total population growth in this decade was 19.90 percent while in previous decade it was 28.06 percent. The population of Haryana forms 2.09 percent of India in 2011. In 2001, the figure was 2.06 percent.

(b) Haryana Literacy Rate 2011

Literacy rate in Haryana has seen upward trend and is 75.55 percent as per 2011 population census. Of that, male literacy stands at 84.06 percent while female literacy is at 56.91 percent. In 2001, literacy rate in Haryana stood at 67.91 percent of which male and female were 76.10 percent and 59.61 percent literate respectively.

(c) Haryana Density 2011

Total area of Haryana is 44,212 sq. km. Density of Haryana is 573 per sq km which is higher than national average 382 per sq km. In 2001, density of Haryana was 478 per sq km, while nation average in 2001 was 324 per sq km.

Haryana Sex Ratio

Sex Ratio in Haryana is 879 i.e. for each 1000 male, which is below national average of 940 as per census 2011. In 2001, the sex ratio of female was 861 per 1000 males in Haryana.

State	Total Population	Rural Population	Urban Population	Rural Pop Percentage	Urban Pop Percentage
Haryana	2,53,53,081	1,65,31,493	88,21,588	65.21	34.79

Rural Development Department, Haryana

The Department of Rural Development through the District Rural Development Agencies is implementing Special Beneficiary Oriented Schemes, Wage Employment Programmes and Area Development Programmes. The Government of India from the year 1999-2000 has restructured/modified most of the Rural Development Schemes. Besides this, the Government of India has also changed the funding pattern of all the schemes from 50:50, 80:20 and 100% and most of the schemes are now being implemented on 75:25 and 90:10 sharing basis between the Central and State Governments respectively. The Special Beneficiary Oriented Schemes, Wage Employment Programmes and Area Development Programmes being implemented by the department of Rural Development are given as under.

**RURAL DEVELOPMENT DEPARTMENT, HARYANA
STATEMENT SHOWING THE SCHEME-WISE OUTLAY FOR THE FINANCIAL YEAR 2015-16**

Sr. No.	Major Heads/Minor Heads of Development (Scheme Wise)	Proposed Outlay of the year 2015-16 (Rs. in Lacs)
A	State share	
1	Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGS)	1800.00
2	Indira Awaas Yojana (IAY)	6000.00
3	DRDA Admn.	650.00
4	Integrated Wasteland Management Programme (IWMP)	550.00
5	NRLM/SGSY	1200.00
6	Monitoring Cell	40.00
7	Pay to JGSY Staff (At State Headquarter)	55.00
8	Pay to Gram Sevikas	300.00
9	Information Technology (IT)	5.00
	Sub Total	100600.00
B	Centre Share	
1	MGNREGS	25000.00
2	IAY	18000.00
3	IWMP	5000.00
4	BRGF	3300.00
5	MPLADS	7500.00
6	NRLM/SGSY (including DRDA Admn.)	3500.00
	Sub Total	62300.00
	GRAND TOTAL	72900.00

District Rural Development Agency

The District Rural Development Agency (DRDA) has traditionally been the principal organ at the District level to oversee the implementation of different anti poverty programmes. The primary objective of DRDA Schemes is to professionalize the DRDAs so that they are able to effectively manage the anti poverty programmes of the Ministry of

Rural Development and interact effectively with other agencies. The Department of Rural Development is implementing a number of programmes in rural areas through the state Governments for poverty reduction, employment generation, rural infrastructure habitant development, provision of basic minimum services etc.

Programmes implemented by the DRDA

- Panchayati Raj
- Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana (PMGSY)
- Swarnjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana (SGSY)
- Sampoorna Gramin Rozgar Yojana (SGRY)
- Rural Housing (Indira Awaas Yojana)
- DRDA Administration
- Training Schemes
- Promotion of Voluntary Schemes and Social Action Programme, organization of beneficiaries, advancement and dissemination of rural technology through CAPART.
- Monitoring mechanism.
- Swarnjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana (SGSY)
- Indira Awaas Yojana (IAY)
- Sampooran Grameen Rozgar Yojana (SGRY)
- Watershed Development Projects/Hariyali Scheme
- Desert Development Programme(DDP)
- Members of Parliament Local Area Development Scheme (MPLADS)
- Rashtriya Sam Vikas Yojana (RSVY)
- Total Sanitation Campaign (TSC)
- Swarnjayanti Shahari Rozgar Yojna (SJSRY)
- Employment Assurance Scheme (EAS)
- National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (NREGS)
- Integrated Wasteland Development Projects (IWDP)
- Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGS)
- Bharat Nirman Rajiv Gandhi Sewa Kendra (BNRGSK)
- National Rural Livelihoods Mission (NRLM)/Aajeevika
- Backward Region Grant Fund
- Intergrated Watershed Management Programme (IWMP)

Comilla Model

The Comilla Model was a rural development programme launched in 1959[1] by the Pakistan Academy for Rural Development (renamed in 1971 the Bangladesh Academy for Rural Development). The Academy, which is located on the outskirts of Comilla town, was founded by Akhter Hameed Khan, the cooperative pioneer who was responsible for developing and launching the programme

The main features of the Comilla Model were:

The promotion of development and of refining of various institutions, both public and private, and establishing a system of interrelationships between them;

- Involvement of both public and private sectors in the process of rural development;
- Development of leadership in every village, including managers, model farmers, women organizers, youth leaders, and village accountants, to manage and sustain the development efforts;
- Development of three basic infrastructures (administrative, physical and organisational);
- Priority on decentralized and coordinated rural administration in coordination with officials of various government departments and the representatives of public organisations.
- Integration and coordination of the various developing services, institutions and projects;
- Education, organisation and discipline;
- Economic planning and technology;
- Development of a stable and progressive agriculture to improve the conditions of the farmers, and provide employment to rural labour force

RIGA Project

The Rural Income Generating Activities (RIGA) Project is a collaboration between the Food and Agriculture Organization, the World Bank, and American University (Washington, DC) that seeks to contribute to the understanding of the income generating activities, both agricultural and non-agricultural, of rural households in developing countries. The RIGA project achieves this by two means. First, through the development of an innovative database of income sources from various developing countries, which is available free of charge to researchers via the project's website. Second, by producing studies and publications that use the database to analyze pressing economic and policy issues.

Purpose

The RIGA Project's purpose is to create an income measure that is comparable within and between countries. According to the RIGA Project website, the key questions addressed by the RIGA Project include:

- What are the relationships between the various Rural Income Generating Activities (RIGAs)?
- What types of RIGAs are associated with poverty reduction?
- What is the relationship between various Rural Non-Farm activities and agriculture?
- What is the link between RIGAs and food security?

In order to answer these questions, the RIGA Project developed a standardized income calculation method that is applied only to country surveys that meet strict criteria of data requirements. The definition of income utilized closely adheres to the one set out by the International Labour Organization. The "Resolution Concerning Household Income and Expenditure Statistics" passed by ILO outlines that household income includes all monetary and in-kind receipts that a household receives, which should include income from wage employment, self-employment, property, own consumption of household goods, and both public and private transfers.[3] Since agriculture remains the principal activity for rural households, the RIGA Project also considers income generated from on-farm activities, both those sold and consumed by the household.

Measures for Rural Development

1. Agricultural output

The most important factor affecting agriculture output is the availability of water. The length of main canals increased only by 42 miles between 1981-1991 and this increase was just 24 miles between 1991-2001. Each additional irrigated hectare of land gives employment to eight additional labourers. If the State gets its due share of water, one lakh hectares of additional area can be brought under irrigation. Thus, State may be able to produce additional grain worth Rs.1000 crore.

- a) Encouraging cultivation under green house sheds: A number of vegetables, flowers and fruits can be grown under greenhouse shed to get high yield. Some private companies provide consultancy, know-how, seeds and marketing facilities with purchase contract. This is known as high capital-low land-low labour-low input high yield strategy.
 - b) Farming can also generate quality employment of 12 lakh persons in supervision, packing and transport of farm output
 - c) The indirect subsidies should be given to promote agriculture
 - e) All direct subsidies should be converted in the indirect ones such as agricultural research and irrigation or water harvesting or water shed management infrastructure or soil conservation or environmental protection or biofertilisers to be in the "Green Box".
2. Panchayats need to be strongly encouraged by subsidies to build and maintain water-harvesting structures, especially in view of the continuing deterioration in the condition of ponds/water tables
 3. The quality of electricity supply is very poor in the rural area and farm sector. This is the main reason that farmers are not willing to pay the power bills. There has been a number of hidden costs in the form of more farm supervision, damage to the water pumps, burning of transformers and increased uncertainty. Since most of the farmers have a flat rate system, thus there is no chance of overuse of the electricity by the farmers. However, this leads to the cultivation of water intensive crops. The SEBs impute all power losses and thefts of all sectors including their own corruption and inefficiencies on the farmers which is not the reality.
 4. It is recommended that the State should use the distributed power production model. The electricity farming by solar power not by photovoltaic method but by focusing of sun rays by a concave mirror, wind-mills, bio-mass energy (using dung), biodiesel or solid plastic wastes generated from urban areas should be the new methods of power generation. The people i.e. farmers, co-operatives, municipal bodies, private parties and shopkeepers should be allowed to produce electricity by any method

5. The Haryana Government should plan all the cities in such a way that they are connected to a hub of villages by circular ring roads with fast transport and connectivity system. The existing 97 urban areas can be connected to the villages by an average peripheral road of 60 kilometres so that even the farthest villager can reach to the city and come back within one hour. This will require building good quality roads of 6500 kilometres. With this kind of strategy, the industrial manufacturers will be induced to start their production units in the rural areas; and the congestion, pollution and rise in property prices and slum areas in the cities will be controlled. The production process will shift from urban to rural areas which can absorb more pollution.
6. The investment in agriculture with new technologies can reduce not only the variable costs of farm outputs in short-run but also the risks of farming
7. A serious policy intervention is required to promote the use of organic, bio/compost fertilisers, organic sprays and integrated pest management practices
8. In the suburban areas or some big villages, where people have the ability to pay, the water supply systems can be handed over to private parties with strict conditions that if they do not invest certain percentage in rain water harvesting, water purification or do not provide good service to the people, the State has the right to change the service provider
9. There is a serious problem of shortage of latrines in Haryana villages. In every village, the government should make best quality latrines and hand over them freely to people who can run them and can recover variable costs
10. There is a great opportunity of generating employment in the rural areas by production of electricity. People should be allowed to produce electricity using bio-mass (dung), biodiesel, solar energy or wind mill. A small bio-mass plant does not cost more than Rs. 40 thousand and can give employment to four unskilled persons. The State can provide training, and the banks can give loans through micro-finance institutions¹⁵. All the schemes of providing incentives to own private assets for self-employment can be connected with family planning schemes. Those who are unemployed and unmarried should be given the asset with the condition that if they have more than two children in future the State can take the asset back
11. The protection of environment can also generate a lot of employment opportunities. The investment in rainwater harvesting structures, community based ponds/johars, etc. should be enhanced.

Rural Infrastructure

a) Rural Roads

Amongst the various components of the infrastructure, the roads in the rural areas have assumed great importance. The development of roads in rural areas would not only provide the basic facility to the villagers but also help in reaching the rural India in its true sense. The rural economy which in other sense is agro economy and the construction of rural roads would provide a major incentive for the development of rural sector, that is, both farm and non-farm sectors. The recent programme of PURA (provision of urban amenities in rural areas) is also an important initiative by the Government of India, in this direction

b) Rural Communication (Telecom)

The second most important component of rural infrastructure is the Rural Telecommunication. After the rural roads, the telecom connectivity forms the most crucial part of the rural connectivity. It connects rural (agro) economy with the rest of the economic development of the country. Irrigation With the limited and scarce irrigation facility, the irrigation potential has not been realised so far. There is enormous potential to be explored in this sector. The wide gap between potential and actual realisation of irrigation is prevailing across the entire rural areas.

c) Shelter-Rural Infrastructure (Rural Housing)

The basic requirement of the rural masses is shelter. For the survival of the human beings, housing is most needed. The housing for the poor in rural areas is most crucial. It provides a dignified living standard and ensures the security to the rural masses.

d) Rural Energy (Rural Electrification)

Power (energy) is the most crucial component of the infrastructure in the rural area. The adequate supply of energy attracts investments, which in turn help in the establishments of various industries in the rural areas. For the up gradation of this component of rural infrastructure, the Government of India has introduced 'Rajiv Gandhi Grameen Vidhyuttikaran Yojana' in the fiscal year of 2005. Under this programme it is planned to provide electricity in all the villages and the habitants in the rural areas, in the coming four years Rural Energy (Bio-Gas Plants) For the provision of clean and unpolluted energy to the rural masses, the programme of biogas plant has been introduced in the State. The

programme was initiated with the two folds objectives. One was to provide energy for the domestic purposes and the second important objective was to generate enriched manure for the use in the agricultural activities.

e) **Renewable Energy**

The State has also implemented various programmes and policies for the exploration of energy through non-conventional and renewable sources. There are many programmes and schemes related to solar energy, biogas, micro hydel and biomass, the State has initiated measures to explore the energy through these sources.

Rural Infrastructure and the Panchayati Raj Institution

The role of Panchayati Raj system has also assumed significant importance in the rural infrastructure development in the State. The financial and administrative powers assigned to PRIs would ensure social security, equality and social justice for the people in the rural areas. The concept of Gram Vikas Samities has been implemented in the States. These bodies are assigned responsibilities of execution of development works in the rural areas.

Haryana Rural Development Fund

Administration Board has been constituted in the State. For the efficient execution of the development works in rural areas.

Nirmal Gram Puraskar

Launched by the GOI for full sanitization and open defecation- free Gram Panchayats in the State. Under the Restructured Rural Sanitation Scheme the government has provided individual toilets and sanitary complex facilities for the women in the rural areas.

Rural Infrastructure and the Institutional Finance

For any development programme, the provision of finances through the mechanism of institutional finance is very essential. In the State of Haryana, the Government has been persuading to the banking institutions to give importance to the Agricultural and Allied Sector, particularly to poverty alleviation programmes.

CONCLUSION

Rural development strategies are a critical component of an inclusive growth strategy for Haryana. Developing a modern rural development strategy for poverty reduction in Haryana in the coming decades requires recognition of institutional and technological changes, as well as of the growing role of a broadly defined and diversified agricultural system. Furthermore, the rural poor need to participate in the development and implementation of the relevant policies and programs, which need to ensure.

- gender equity
- inclusion of minorities
- participation of the poorest in markets and in the provision of services

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